

SOUVENIR

ONE DAY NATIONAL SEMINAR ON ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN AQUACULTURE

(05th March 2021)

PG DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY

SYED AMMAL ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE

Affiliated To Alagappa University - Karaikudi

Dr. E.M.Abdullah Nagar, Kootampuli

Pullangudi (Po), Ramanathapuram-623513

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One Day National Seminar on
Entrepreneurship in aquaculture

05 March 2021

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Editors

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Organized by

PG DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY

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Message

It gives me an immense happy in receiving your invitation for the one day national seminar on Entrepreneurship Aquaculture, organized by the department of Zoology on 05th March 2021. I convey my best wishes for the grand success of the seminar.

(Mr.A.Chelladurai Abdullah B.Sc.,)

SYED AMMAL ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE

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Message

I feel extremely happy to know that the department of Zoology of our college is conducting a seminar on Entrepreneurship Aquaculture on 05th March 2021. I also feel very proud to know that a souvenir is going to be released on that day.

My best wishes for the success of the seminar

(Mrs.A.Rajathi Abdullah M.A., B.Ed.,)

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Message

I feel very happy that the PG Department of Zoology is conducting one day national Seminar on Entrepreneurship in Aquaculture on 05 March 2021. It becomes very important that everybody must be helpful Entrepreneurship in Aquaculture. In this seminar some successful development of entrepreneurship in fisheries and aquaculture sector are presented and specific areas where there is new scope for entrepreneurship have been discussed. I have to appreciate the HOD and faculty members for their efforts to conduct this type of seminar. I congratulate them and bless them to conduct many more conferences in a grand manner..

(Dr.SVS. Amanulla Hameed M.Sc., M.Phil., Ph.D., FAZ)

PG DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY
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PREFACE

Social entrepreneurs are the drivers of change, who find creative solution to societal problems, which are efficient, sustainable, and transparent and have measurable impact. Fisheries and aquaculture sector is an important sector for livelihoods, food and nutritional security. In this seminar, some successful development of entrepreneurship in fisheries and aquaculture sector are presented and specific areas where there is new scope for entrepreneurship have been discussed. There is immense scope for aquaculture entrepreneurship in this important food production sector, which is important for overall social and economic development and would help in achieving livelihood, food and nutritional security. This seminar was participated by more than 150 participants with a total of 25 presented papers. The seminar also invited the prominent scientists in fisheries and marine science mainly in the topics of marine sciences, fisheries management, aquaculture and fish processing technology. The seminar theme was “One day national seminar on entrepreneurship in aquaculture” covered broad topics in fisheries and marine science such as entrepreneurship aquaculture, fish diseases, collection and identification, fisheries biology, fisheries management and fisheries socio-economics. This proceeding provides an opportunity for readers to engage with refereed papers presented on 05 March 2021 of the Department of Zoology, Syed Ammal Arts and Science College, Ramanathapuram. Therefore, in this proceeding, readers might discover the recent issue and results of research in the broad topics of fisheries and marine sciences. We would like to deeply appreciate all of parties for the successful of the seminar. We expressed out deep sense of gratitude to Mr. A. Chelladurai Abdullah, Secretary and other management committee members of Syed Ammal trust who manage the Syed Ammal Arts and Science College for their encouragement and support. We deeply express our gratitude for organizing committee, keynote and invited speakers, reviewers, editors and editing staffs for fully dedication, tireless efforts and continuing hard work along the seminar events and the process of this proceeding publication.

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MESSAGE

Fisheries and aquaculture is an important sector in India, providing employment to millions of people and contributes to the food security of the country. Presently, India ranks third in aquaculture and fisheries production, contributing 1.07% to the national GDP and 5.30% to the agriculture GDP. Fisheries and aquaculture is one of the fastest-growing industries in the World and has been playing an important role in the economic development front on account of its contribution to food and nutritional security, national income, employment opportunities as well as generating livelihood options. It is the primary source of animal protein for billions of people Worldwide, where capture fishery and aquaculture serves the livelihoods of more than 10% of the global population especially in the more economically backward rural areas. Fish, being an excellent source of protein and many other essential fatty acids and micronutrients, plays a particular role in human nutrition by providing a valuable and nutritious contribution to a diversified and healthy diet. The overall demand of fish for consumption is expected to be increased, with more and more people shifting their food habits towards protein-rich diets. In India, 56% of the Indian population are fish eaters, and the per capita availability of fish is 9.85 Kg. However, unfortunately Indian aquaculture system facing several challenges in cope up with sustainable production of fish food which include availability of good quality seeds, land leasing tenure, water availability, feed availability, access to technology at grass root level, climate change and pollution are the prominent constraints of aquaculture development in India. The inadequate availability of quality seeds, lack of nutritionally superior live feeds during the larval phase and poor water quality as the top three constraints affecting aquaculture, others being short supply of water, high cost of supplementary feed, high cost of electricity, non-availability of skilled labour, prevalence of disease outbreak, high mortality during culture, low farm gate price, problem of direct selling to buyers, low productivity, poor quality of seeds and low net returns. The use of modern technology for increasing production and productivity, encouraging research and development in innovative technology generation using indigenous knowledge according to the needs of the farmers are highly essential nowadays. In this context, I strongly believe that this National Seminar on Entrepreneurship in Aquaculture (EIA-2021) would serve as platform for the scientists, researchers, academicians, students, stakeholders etc., to deliberate on the various issues of aquaculture and innovative technological solutions towards the sustainable aquaculture. Besides, this seminar would provide an awareness among youth to progress them as entrepreneurs.

I appreciate and congratulate the authorities of Syed Ammal Arts and Science College, Ramanathapuram especially Dr. M. Thayalan, HOD of Zoology & Organizing Secretary to organize this seminar at the time of need.

P. SANTHANAM

SREE KRISHNA COLLEGE

GURUVAYUR

P.G. DEPARTMENT OF BOTANY & RESEARCH CENTRE

Ariyannur P.O., Thrissur District Kerala State - 680 102
[Nationally reaccredited by NAAC with 'A' Grade CGPA 3.2]

I am happy to know that the Department of Zoology, Syed Ammal Arts and Science College, Ramanathapuram, is organizing a National Seminar on Entrepreneurship in Aquaculture (EIA 2021), on 5th March 2021, with an extra bit of joy for being a part of this program. I wish this seminar would serve as an appropriate forum to exchange and share the experiences, ideas, and latest research results on all aspects of entrepreneurship-oriented aquaculture. The organizers are publishing a Souvenir with ISBN and seminar proceedings, which is highly appreciable. The students will be highly benefitted with this kind gesture of theirs.

This seminar will surely be an eye opener for all those students, who have an entrepreneur in them, the impact of which will be an efficient and sustainable future by the younger generation.

I congratulate the Principal and the Organizers for organizing the Seminar on such a valuable and need of the hour topic.

I wish the One Day National Seminar a grand success.

Guruvayur
01.03.2021

Dr. Gayathri G

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SEaweEDS FOR SOCIETAL EMPOWERMENT

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ABSTRACT

Seaweeds are the only source for the production of phycocolloids such as agar, carrageenan and algin. The agar is extracted from red algae like species of *Gracilaria*, *Gelidium*, *Pterocladia* and *Gelidiella acerosa*, algin is extracted from brown algae *Sargassum* and *Turbinaria* and carrageenan from some other red algae such as species of *Eucheuma*, *Chondrus*, *Hypnea* and *Gigartina*. Natural resources of economic seaweeds are abundant along the southeast coast of India especially along the Gulf of Mannar. Over-utilization of natural stocks coupled with short supply of commercially important seaweeds on the one hand, and their loss due to natural calamities like cyclones on the other hand, has necessitated the seaweed cultivation in India. Understanding the importance of seaweed cultivation, the Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute (CSMCRI) has developed viable techniques for the large scale cultivation of agarophytes *Gracilaria edulis*, *G. dura*, *G. salicornia* and carrageenophytes *Hypnea musciformis* and *Kappaphycus alvarezii* edible and pharmaceutically important green seaweeds e.g. *Enteromorpha* and *Ulva*. *Kappaphycus alvarezii* is being cultivated at commercial scale by rural fisherfolk in Ramanathapuram, Tuticorin and Pudukkottai district. Efforts are being taken for implementing commercial cultivation of other economic seaweeds with the support of Government and seaweed based industries. The present paper discussed about the socio economic benefit achieved by the coastal fisher population through seaweed cultivation.

MARINE COPEPODS: A NOVEL APPROACH TOWARDS THE SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE

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ABSTRACT

India recorded a fish production of around 12.38 million metric tonnes in 2018 with aquaculture production contributing to 57%. It is well known that wild catches are diminishing alarmingly in the recent past due to over exploitation, climate change and pollution. According to a UNEP report, if the world continues on its current path of overfishing, it would become uneconomical to exploit the fish stock in the ocean by the year 2050 and several fish species might become extinct. Augmenting aquaculture production is the only way by which the protein requirement of the fish-eating population can be generated and the scenario mentioned above can be avoided. However, unfortunately the development of aquaculture in India has been seriously troubled by vulnerable diseases owing to lack of quality fish seeds due to the short of nutritionally balanced feeds during their larval stages. For a sustained growth of the aquaculture industry, regular supply of sufficient quantity and good quality seeds are the prerequisites. Disease resistant seeds are those that ensure high growth rate, low mortality and stress resistance during the culture in grow out system. The use of live feeds for fish seed production is well established with *Artemia* and rotifer being the most common among them. Although *Artemia* and rotifer are being widely used as live food, by no means it is the optimal live food organism in terms of nutritional requirement of fish larvae. Hence the production of highly vulnerable larvae remains a bottleneck in the commercial culture of many fish and shrimp in India. Enrichment of *Artemia* and rotifer are widely adopted to overcome the problem of inferior nutrition supply. But there are still other nutrient deficiencies in the enriched *Artemia* nauplii and rotifers, such as free amino acids availability. Furthermore, the biological composition of *Artemia* and rotifers are not stable even after enrichment. Moreover the enrichment with commercial emulsifier can enhance the cost of production of fish larvae. Traditionally, antibiotics have been used to treat fish

diseases. However, the use of antibiotics causes problems to cultivable organisms and consumers. Hence, the emergence of immune exciting feed is need of the hour. It is well accepted that the copepods are rich sources of essential amino acids (EAA), highly unsaturated fatty acids (HUFA), enzymes, antioxidant, astaxanthin and vitamins. High nutritional profile of copepods could counteract the compromised immune response capacity caused by stressful conditions and enhance the resistance in fish larvae. Various researchers have attempted to mass culture the different species of copepods and used them as feed for larval production of various fish and shrimp species in foreign countries (Farhadian *et al.*, 2009; Olivotto *et al.*, 2010). However, only limited attempts have been made in Indian subcontinent on the culture and utilization of copepods in fish and shrimp larviculture in laboratory scale (Santhanam and Perumal, 2012; Dinesh Kumar *et al.*, 2017). The systematic use of copepods in hatcheries not yet practiced so far in India due to lack of technology for the large scale continuous production. In this context, an attempt has been made at the Marine Planktonology and Aquaculture Laboratory, Department of Marine Science of Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, on the high density continuous production of domesticated marine copepods and their use in sustainable larval production of commercial important fin fishes and shell fishes.

Keywords: Marine copepod, Artemia, Rotifer, EAA, HUFA, Sustainable aquaculture

CAPTIVE BREEDING OF MARINE ORNAMENTAL FISHES WITH REFERENCE TO CLOWN FISHES

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ABSTRACT

The trade in marine ornamental fishes is valued at over a billion dollars annually and comprises thousands of species. Approximately 4 million marine ornamental fishes per year during 2014 and 2017. Susceptible species were identified using the number of traded specimens, trends in the trade volume, IUCN Red List conservation status, as well as vulnerability according to FishBase. The only alternative to preserve the ornamental stock is captive breeding. India is a repository of more than 200 varieties of marine ornamental fishes of which more than 50 are very bright and have export potential. Among these, the clown fishes or anemone fishes belonging to the family Pomacentridae, comprising of genera *Amphiprion* and *Premnas* have always been the most popular and sought-after group of marine ornamentals due to their beautiful colour, small size, hardiness, longevity, proclivity to live in association with sea anemone, interesting display behaviour and adaptability to life in captivity. Altogether, 28 species of clown fishes were reported from the different geographical locations of the world. The members of the family Pomacentridae, commonly known as damselfishes and anemonefishes are a diverse group of marine fishes found in tropical oceans, and have very high demand in the marine ornamental fish trade. The family includes 29 genera and 350 recognized species living mainly in coral reef environments. Pomacentrids have been divided into four subfamilies: Amphiprioninae, Chrominae, Lepidozyginae and Pomacentrinae. Under the genera *Amphiprion*, so far 27 species have been reported world wide. The maroon clown *Premnas biaculeatus* is the sole member in the genus *Premnas*. Clownfishes are the most longstanding and intensively cultured family of marine ornamentals. For successful culture of clownfish, the following things are vital, Healthy brooders, Water quality, Nutritional food & Live feed, Suitable physical environment – light, temperature and ambient environment and Disease management.

SINGLE CELL PROTEINS- A NEW CHOICE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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ABSTRACT

Proteins are sources of nitrogen and aminoacids for humans and other organisms as well. They enable us to survive by helping to build new structural and functional proteins. The global demand for food resources, especially proteins, are still increasing. This demand is for direct human consumption and as animal feedants. But, the food production is not able to meet the growing demand. When the production becomes much less than the demand, sustainable and new solutions turn out to be the need of the hour. The potential option would be the use of single cell proteins, the proteins produced in microbial and algal cells. Single cell proteins (SCPs) are gaining momentum owing to its low- cost raw material and high nutritional value, for being used as fish feedants. Nowadays, the focus has been shifted to valorization of side streams using the micro organisms, to improve the protein content, which in turn can be used as fish feedants as well. SCPs are the better choice for starting an entrepreneurship as they are cheap and requires only certain space for them to cultured. As the sources are microbes, a huge amount of these proteins can be produced in a very short time and minimal infrastructure like bioreactors. There are different methods of microbial culturing with much economic value. Fermentation, enzymolysis, air drying and sterilization are some mechanisms by which these SCPs can be cultured. Moreover, schemes are available and offered by various nationalized banks, across the country for starting an entrepreneurship, even at a small scale level. Proper communication and transparency in the bank dealings can make you a successful entrepreneur.

**SCREENING METHODS TO DETERMINE ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF SOME
MEDICINAL PLANTS COMMONLY USED IN TAMIL NADU (SOUTH INDIA)
AGAINST SELECTED FISH PATHOGENIC MICROBE**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was observe in the antibacterial activity of aqueous methanolic extracts of 10 plants against fish pathogen gram negative *Aeromonas hydrophila* by using disc diffusion and well in seed method. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimal bacterial concentration was determined by agar well diffusion method and agar dilution method. The bacterium was susceptible to different plant extracts. *Acorus calamus*, *Indigofera aspalathoides* and *Coleous aromaticaus* showed antibacterial activity against all the tested bacteria. The extract of *Acorus calamus* showed maximum antibacterial activity of the 10 plant extracts used. It is clear from the results of the present studies that the plant extracts have great potential as antimicrobial compounds against bacteria. However, there is a need of further research to isolate the active ingredients for further pharmacological evaluation.

Keywords: *Aeromonas hydrophila*, Antibacterial, *Acorus calamus*, Medicinal plants.

**SEASONAL VARIATION AND DISTRIBUTION OF PHYTOPLANKTON IN
DEVIPATTINAM AREAS PALK – STRAIGHT SOUTH EAST COAST OF INDIA**

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ABSTRACT

In Phytoplankton the species composition and the density depend upon the variety of environmental parameters. The hydrological parameter such as nutrients, qualitative analysis and the species composition showed marked seasonal variations. There showed a negative correlation between salinity and phytoplankton. The surface water temperature varied from 27° C to 32 ° C. The present Study showed that the increase in phytoplankton composition as the growth depended upon the temperature abundance. The above were play in an vital in the abundance of phytoplankton. Hence the present observation showed a significant change between salinity and Phytoplankton diversity.

Key words: Phytoplankton, Temperature, Nutrients.

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**EFFICACY OF VERMICOMPOSTING OF AQUATIC WEED AND EFFECT OF
VERMICOMPOST ON GROWTH AND YIELD PARAMETERS OF
HIBISCUS ESCULENTUS (LADY FINGER)**

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ABSTRACT

As India is an agriculture based country, farmers need suitable resources to replenish soil fertility and maintain the productivity of soil. Really, the green revolution has popularized the use of chemical fertilizers to achieve higher productivity. But due to continuous and indiscriminate use of fertilizers, the natural fertility of soil has been lost and this activity has contaminated our soil, water and food. Therefore farmers are in need of searching another to replace the chemical fertilizers. In recent days, the use of organic inputs like vermicomposting, biofertilizers and biopesticides is becoming popular in the world wide. There is a need of effective technology to deal with disposal of wastes which continues to be a challenge as population increases. The aim of the present research was to study the effect of vermicompost prepared from water hyacinth, leaf litters and cow dung on growth and yield of *Hibiscus esculentus* under greenhouse conditions. Vermicomposting of organic wastes was carried out by using surface burrowing type of earth worms (*Lampito marutii*). The pot experiment was conducted with four treatments via T₁ Control, T₂- Cow dung, T₃ – Leaf litter vermicompost. The results showed significant variations in plant growth parameters of vermicompost. The growth characters of lady finger such as plant height, number of leaves per plant were observed at 15th day, 30th day, and 45th day from the date of planting. There was maximum value of growth

parameters observed in leaf litter vermicompost followed by Eichhornia vermicompost, cow dung vermicompost and control. Yield parameters also showed the similar trend of growth parameters. The investigation clearly reveals that the biochemical properties of vermicompost play major role in growth and yield of *H.esculentus*.

Key words: Vermicompost, *Hibiscus esculentus*, water hyacinth.

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SEASONAL VARIATION OF XENOBIOTIC ACCUMULATION IN FRESH WATER FISH *ORECHROMISNILOTICUS* FROM THE SELECTED WETLANDS AROUND COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The contamination of aquatic ecosystems by heavy metals has become a worldwide concern. This is because of their ability and persisting nature to accumulate in aquatic organisms and especially in fish which is considered a major protein source of livelihood for human populations. Therefore, an assessment of heavy metal contamination (Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Ni and Zn,) in water and food fish species, *Oreochromisniloticus* collected from three different wetlands around Coimbatore district. Heavy metal Concentrations were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The metal concentration in water and fish exhibited a significant seasonal variation. The results showed the mean concentration of metals in the following order Zn > Cu > Ni > Cr > Cd > Pb. All the metal concentrations were recorded high during monsoon and low during summer season. The concentration of heavy metals in both water and fish samples were above than the World Health Organization (WHO) set limit. The result of this study indicates there should be a need for regular monitoring approach towards sustainable management of the wetland ecosystem. This will curb the aquatic pollution which is a health risk for people consuming aquatic resources contaminated by heavy metals.

Key words: Heavy metals, pollution, seasonal variation, *Oreochromisniloticus*,

GIS BASED ASSESSMENT ON DISTRIBUTION AND DIVERSITY OF BENTHOS IN PALK BAY, SOUTHEAST COAST OF INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Benthos – bottom dwelling organisms in the marine environment. Assessment was made in Palk bay which have rich seagrass bed. Polychaete worms, crustaceans, mollusca and meiofauna were collected at six sampling points for the period of six months in Mutiveeranpattinam seashore region of Palk bay. The collected benthos was identified at species level with identification keys. In this study, 35 different species of macrofauna and 50 species of meiofauna were recorded. Maximum numbers of macrofauna were recorded in the month of January and minimum in October. The macrofauna was maximum in the month of February and minimum in December. In the present study, also reported that the physico-chemical factors such as Temperature, pH, salinity and dissolved oxygen of those study periods. The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis such as Simpson index, Shannon Index, Diversity index, Species richness & evenness, standard deviation and correlation using SPSS software. Hydro biological and nutrients were analysed and understood that they play crucial role on the distribution of benthos. Geographical Information System (GIS) based contours models were prepared for efficient understanding.

Keywords: GIS, Palk bay, Simpson index, Shannon index Hydrobiology.

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SCREENING OF ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF MARINE SPONGE***EPHYDTIA FLUVIATILIS*****Jothika .C and M.Muruganandam**

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Abstract

The marine environment is a reservoir of variety of organisms and their products are bioactive compounds, secondary metabolites with diverse chemical structures. Many chemicals are unique compounds of marine origin with different organisms. Biologically activity has been isolated and a number of them are under investigation. Sponges (porifera) are one of the richest sources of both biologically active secondary metabolites and chemical diversity. The antifungal compounds screening in marine sponges are a current research in many drug industry. Screening of organic extracts from marine sponges is a common approach to identify compounds of biochemical importance. In this study *Ephydtia fluviatilis* marine sponge was collected and prepared cold extracts then study then antifungal activity. The maximum antifungal activity was observed in N-butyl alcohol and petroleum ether extracts of this sponge. It will useful to new antifungal drug preparations

Keywords: Marine sponge, antifungal activity, *Ephydtia flaviatilis*

BIOEFFICACY OF BIOSYNTHEZIZED AGNO₃ NANOPARTICLES USING LEAF EXTRACTS OF *ACALYPHA INDICA* AND *ANDROGRAPHIS PANICULATA* AGAINST *CULEX QUINQUEFASCIATUS*

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ABSTRACT

Mosquito belongs to the phylum Arthropoda and is an important vector for many vector-borne diseases. It causes millions of death among the population worldwide. Over the last decades, climate change, population growth, deforestation, habitat invasion and insecticide resistance have contributed to the emergence, reemergence and dispersion of several vector-borne diseases. *Culex quinquefasciatus* is commonly known as the southern house mosquito is a medium-sized brown mosquito that exists throughout the tropics and the lower latitudes of temperate regions. Botanical and microbial insecticides have been increasingly used for mosquito control because of their efficacy and documented non-toxic effects on non-target organisms. The development of consistent and ecofriendly processes for the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles is an important step in the field of application of nanotechnology. In this study, we investigate on the biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Acalypha indica* and *Andrographis paniculata* leaf extracts and evaluate its lethal concentration (LC50 and LC90) values against fifth instar larvae of the mosquito vectors *C.quinquefasciatus*. The nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Vis spectrum, scanning electron microscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy analysis. Larvae were exposed to three different concentrations (100, 200 & 300µl) of aqueous extracts of synthesized AgNPs for 24 hours. The maximum mortality range was recorded in 300µl of synthesized AgNPs with LC50 32.23 to 64.34 & LC90 18.43 to 52.45 respectively. Both plant leaf synthesized silver nanoparticles found to have prominent bioactivity on mosquito larvae and thus can be used as biocontrol agent to control mosquito population.

Keywords : *Culex quinquefasciatus*, *Acalypha indica* , *Andrographis paniculata*, FTRS, AgNPs

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**STUDIES ON THE INSECT DIVERSITY OF SOUTH EAST COASTS REGION,
RAMANATHAPURAM, TAMILNADU**

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ABSTRACT

The Indian region is recognized as one of the major centers of biodiversity in the world. That the diversity is equally rich at the ecosystem level and at the species level has been well documented by fieldwork carried out by naturalists and professional field biologists during the past 200 years. Today India, occupying 2 percent of global space documents nearly 7 percent of global faunal diversity .Without insect, our lives would be vastly different .Insects pollinate many of our fruits, flowers& vegetables. Especially the largest number of insect identified were Lepidoptera followed by *Hymenoptera*, *Odoanata*, *Hemiptera*, *Orthoptera* and *Coleoptera*. As per the Tamilnadu government record, North East Monsoon Is the Main Source of Irrigation water. Average annual rainfall is 827.0 mm, Average winter Rainfall -67.4 mm;Summer-122.7mm; South West Monsoon – 135.5 and North East Monsoon Rainfall-501.6 mm, Compared to another district Ramanathapuram low rainfall pattern, because of insect diversity level low down these insects direct related to plant population, Thus our study mainly focused on identified classified insect east coastal region, Tamilnadu.

Keywords: Lepidoptera, Entomology, Biodiversity, *Stagmatoptera hyaloptera*.

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DOMESTIC ANIMALS BIO-WASTE EFFECT ON DUCKWEED LEMNA MINOR BIOMASS PRODUCTION

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Abstract

Lemna minor is a floating fresh water aquatic plant. Lemna minor is used as animals fodder bioremediator for waste water nutrient recovery. Lemna minor is a present, Wherever fresh water pond and slow-moving streams occur expect for arctic and sub arctic climates. In this study, different animals biowaste medium was prepared for culture of duckweed lemna minor. Animal biowaste have more nitrogen content and it is very much helpful to culture of common duckweed. In this work six experiments were conducted among these experiment five experiment were mainly deals with culture of duckweed with help of various animals biowaste. In the sixth experiment, duckweed based pellet feed was prepared and given to various group domestic animals then feed accept once were studied. In the present study cowdung and poultry waste enhance the growth of duckweed lemna minor . The second maximum duckweed production observation in goat waste treatments. The rabbit waste was not suitable for duckweed culture. If increase the cowdung in medium, the biomass production was slowly increased. But in poultry waste treatment 2.5g treatment and goat waste treatment 2.0g treatment produces higher biomass production. The duckweed based feed was accepted by all domestic animal so it is helpful to reduce feed cost and increase the profit to small scale formers in rurel areas.

Key words: Duckweed, Lemnaminor, Animal biowaste.

GENETIC DIVERSITY OF *RHIZOBIUM LEGUMINOSARUM* ISOLATES AS REVEALED BY RANDOM AMPLIFIED POLYMORPHIC DNA ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Vigna mungo is an important food legume suitable for dry regions of most of the country. Leguminous plants are fortunate to avail the atmospheric nitrogen by the symbiotic soil bacteria belonging to the genera *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Sinorhizobium*, *Azorhizobium* and *Allorhizobium*. Among these biological nitrogen fixers, *Rhizobium* is the dominant and common genus of leguminous plants throughout the world. Analysis of the genetic structure of *Rhizobium* populations have practical importance since the results can be used to access the fate of the strains. Twelve different isolates of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* isolated from the root nodules of *Vigna mungo* were characterized by PCR-RAPD to understand the extent of genetic diversity. There are twenty primers tested RAPD KitA5 and KitA12 produced clear, consistent and scorable RAPD fragments for the isolates of *R. leguminosarum*. Among these two primers, RAPD KitA5 produced the most polymorphic amplification patterns that could distinguish almost all the isolates from each other. The UPGMA based dendrogram groups the twelve isolates into different clusters. The genetic similarity of 100% was recorded among the isolates of IV and X and the least of 25% was recorded among isolates V and VII. The RAPD profile of different isolates of *R. leguminosarum* generated by Kit A5 primer revealed great degree of genetic polymorphism among the isolates.

Key Words: *Rhizobium leguminosarum*, *Vigna mungo*, Genetic diversity, PCR-RAPD, UPGMA

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BIO –FERTILIZER DEVELOPMENT THROUGH DOMESTIC ANIMAL’S BIOWASTES

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ABSTRACT

Bio-based wastes can be used to fertilizers plants in the form of by-products to add value to fertilizer formulation and proper utilization of livestock waste into biogas, compost and vermi compost making can be very useful to increase crop yield and sustainability. Animal manure is a valuable resource. Several techniques ranging from simple, low-cost to complex strategies are available for proper handling of animal manure. In the study a different domestic bio- waste were collected and shadow dried and these were mixed with adequate amount of soil and put in a tray for a week after that these treatment were used for experiment First seed onion were completely clean with tap water then they were introduced into the soil of individuals Biofertilizer treatment and greens seeds were introduced. At the end of the experiment all the treatment biomass of onion and greens were recorded. In the study various animal blowaste based bio-fertilizer effects on growth of onion and slender amaranthus green were analysed. Based on these studies organic animal bio waste based bio-fertilizer are best to garden plants. This bio-fertilizer have produce no pollution, eco-friendly, least cost and univershelly available in rurale areas.

Key words: Green Slender Amaranths, Onion, Bio-fertiliser

BIOEFFICACY OF BIOSYNTHESED AGNO₃ NANOPARTICLES USING LEAF EXTRACTS OF ACALYPHA INDICA AND ANDROGRAPHIS PANICULATA AGAINST CULEX QUINQUEFASCIATUS

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ABSTRACT

Mosquito belongs to the phylum Arthropoda and is an important vector for many vector-borne diseases. It causes millions of death among the population worldwide. Over the last decades, climate change, population growth, deforestation, habitat invasion and insecticide resistance have contributed to the emergence, reemergence and dispersion of several vector-borne diseases. *Culex quinquefasciatus* is commonly known as the southern house mosquito is a medium-sized brown mosquito that exists throughout the tropics and the lower latitudes of temperate regions. Botanical and microbial insecticides have been increasingly used for mosquito control because of their efficacy and documented non-toxic effects on non-target organisms. The development of consistent and ecofriendly processes for the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles is an important step in the field of application of nanotechnology. In this study, we investigate on the biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Acalypha indica* and *Andrographis paniculata* leaf extracts and evaluate its lethal concentration (LC50 and LC90) values against fifth instar larvae of the mosquito vectors *C.quinquefasciatus*. The nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Vis spectrum, scanning electron microscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy analysis. Larvae were exposed to three different concentrations (100, 200 & 300µl) of aqueous extracts of synthesized AgNPs for 24 hours. The maximum mortality range was recorded in 300µl of synthesized AgNPs with LC50 32.23 to 64.34 & LC90 18.43 to 52.45 respectively. Both plant leaf synthesized silver nanoparticles found to have prominent bioactivity on mosquito larvae and thus can be used as biocontrol agent to control mosquito population.

Keywords : *Culex quinquefasciatus*, *Acalypha indica* , *Andrographis paniculata*, FTRS, AgNPs

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STUDIES ON THE PHYTOCHEMICAL EVOLUTION, ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *PISONIA ALBA* PLANT EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

It is estimated that is the number of between 75number of between 750,000 and 1,000,000 plant species On the World. The 500,000 Of them have been identification and named. Around 2000 new flowering plant species are identified and named in each year. The number of plant which have been used for treatment since ancient times shows a steady increase. According to a report released by the World Health Organization (WHO), the number of plants used for much treatment is estimated to be around 20,000. Based on current evidences preclinical studies to suggest that some medicinal properties (Bioactive) have been identified to possess preliminary screening, Antioxidant activity and Antibacterial activity of select *Pisonia alba* plant leaf is widely distributed in the east a costal region, Ramanathapuram, Tamilnadu, India. These herbal drugs when combined with conventional antioxidant and antibacterial therapies may prove to be helpful to synergize the bioactive compound effect, and reduce the side effects association with conventional drugs.

Keywords: Phytochemical analysis, Antibacterial analysis, Antioxidant, Screening.

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ASSESSMENT ON DIVERSITY OF PLANKTON IN PALK BAY, SOUTH EAST COAST INDIA -GIS BASED APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

Planktons are free floating microorganisms and that are widely distributed in the marine and estuarine environments. Marine plankton includes Putiplankton and zooplankton drifting in the surface of ocean, brackish water and estuaries. The collection of phytoplankton and zooplanktons were collected at six sampling points for the period of three months at take up present work on Palk bay in Mudiveeranpattinam seashore region. 30 species were collected and identified, the dominant one are *Cladoceron* sp., *Coscinodiscus nitidus*, *Ceratinum extensum* and *Asterionella japonica* during the study among 15 species of zooplanktons of *Copepod*, *Daphnia*, *Acartia clausi* and Zoea larva. These species are seen abundantly in this region. Hydro biological and nutrients were analyzed that understood that they play crucial role on the distribution of planktons. Geographical Information System (GIS) based contours models were prepared for efficient understanding.

Keywords: GIS, Palk bay, Contours, Marine planktons, Hydrobiology

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GENETIC DIVERSITY OF *RHIZOBIUM LEGUMINOSARUM* ISOLATES AS REVEALED BY RANDOM AMPLIFIED POLYMORPHIC DNA ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Vigna mungo is an important food legume suitable for dry regions of most of the country. Leguminous plants are fortunate to avail the atmospheric nitrogen by the symbiotic soil bacteria belonging to the genera *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Sinorhizobium*, *Azorhizobium* and *Allorhizobium*. Among these biological nitrogen fixers, *Rhizobium* is the dominant and common genus of leguminous plants throughout the world. Analysis of the genetic structure of *Rhizobium* populations have practical importance since the results can be used to access the fate of the strains Twelve different isolates of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* isolated from the root nodules of *Vigna mungo* were characterized by PCR-RAPD to understand the extent of genetic diversity. There are twenty primers tested RAPD KitA5 and KitA12 produced clear, consistent and scorable RAPD fragments for the isolates of *R. leguminosarum*. Among these two primers, RAPD KitA5 produced the most polymorphic amplification patterns that could distinguish almost all the isolates from each other. The UPGMA based dendrogram groups the twelve isolates into different clusters. The genetic similarity of 100% was recorded among the isolates of IV and X and the least of 25% was recorded among isolates V and VII. The RAPD profile of different isolates of *R. leguminosarum* generated by Kit A5 primer revealed great degree of genetic polymorphism among the isolates.

Key Words: *Rhizobium leguminosarum*, *Vigna mungo*, Genetic diversity, PCR-RAPD,

UPGMA

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**STUDIES ON THE FISH DIVERSITY OF SOUTH EAST COASTS REGION,
RAMANATHAPURAM, TAMIL NADU**

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ABSTRACT

Coastal aquaculture has been recognized as an important tool for employment generation & a vital source of food supply for meeting the food security & nutritional requirements of our growing population. In the context of increasing food security in the modern world, fish & fishery products are considered to be among the safest foods of animal origin. The basic facts of diversity through species discovery 7 descriptions are mostly complete for some areas of the world and for many families of fishes. Fishes constitute more than half of all vertebrates, with over 31,000 valid species, and of these over half are marine fishes. Fishes form important element in the economy of many nations as they form a staple item in the diet of many people. Since freshwater fish has been identified as a suitable tool for biological assessment due to its easy identification and economic value measure has to be taken to conserve these bio-indicators. As per the data of the above issues, there is an urgent need for a proper investigation like Morphometric traits ProL-pre-orbital, Length pool, Post orbital Length, Survey study & documentation of fish diversity of the east coastal region, Tamilnadu, India. No attempt has been made in the diversity of fish landing center.

Keywords: *Elasmo branchii*, *Pisces*, Ramanathapuram, Morphometric, Economy.

GIS BASED INTERPOLATION CONTOUR MODELS ON THE ASSESSMENT OF HYDROBIOLOGY IN PALK BAY, SOUTH EAST COAST INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Hydrobiology is the science of water around the life. The water samples were collected at six sampling points for the period of three months at take up present work on Palk bay in Mutiveeranpattinam seashore region. Identified 8 different type of into collection of samplings.The parameters of pH,salinity,dissolved oxygen,temperature, Nitrate, Nitrate and Phosphate are present in the particular amount of water sample.Hydrobiology is play a major role in lives of marine organisms.The sample collection is based on GIS method contour models were prepared for efficient understanding.

Keywords:Hydrobiology, Palk bay, GIS, Contour method.

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ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY STUDIES ON STARFISH

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ABSTRACT

Many studies have shown an increasing frequency of systematic fungal infection within the last decades in advanced human immunodeficiency virus infected patients and other patients with deficient immune system. Furthermore, with the emergence of new Triazol- resistant strains of fungi, new compound must still be screened in search of fungicidal effect, with a broad spectrum of activity and without side effects. The marine environment is an exceptional reservoir of a wide variety of organisms which are prolific producers of novel bioactive compound, .Secondary metabolites with diverse chemical structures .Screening of organic extract from marine organisms is a common approach to identify compounds of biomedical importance. The antifungal compounds screening in marine resources are a current research in many drug industry. However there are limited reports present in bioactive compounds of marine animals. Many researchers reported that there is a mixture of antimicrobial protein present in fish tissue and internal organs of fish. They also reported that marine shrimp's muscles and exoskeleton extracts contain antifungal activity .In this study starfish was selected and with the help of various organic solvent, starfish extracts were prepared. After that, antifungal activities of all the extracts were studied. The maximum activity observed in ethanol extract .The second maximum activity was observed in aqueous extract of starfish. These antifungal compounds are recommended to drugs preparation.

Keywords: Starfish, Antifungal activity, Marine drug.

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**LARVICIDAL ACTIVITY OF BIOSYNTHESIZED $AgNO_3$
NANOPARTICLES USING LEAF EXTRACT OF *ANDROGRAPHIS
PANICULATA* AND *ACALYPHA INDICA* AGAINST *Aedes Aegypti***

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ABSTRACT

Mosquitoes are one of the most medically significant groups of vectors, having an ability to transmit parasites and pathogens that can have devastating impacts on humans. *A. aegypti* (Yellow Fever Mosquito) is a strongly anthropophilic and synanthropic species which due to its capacity to thrive in human settlements, has been able to expand its distribution all along the tropical and subtropical regions of the globe. The development of reliable and ecofriendly processes for the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles is an important step in the field of application of nanotechnology. In this study, we focus on the biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Andrographis paniculata* leaf extract and evaluate its lethal concentration (LC50 and LC90) values against fifth instar larvae of the mosquito vectors, *Aedes aegypti*. The nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Vis spectrum, scanning electron microscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy analysis. Larvae were exposed to three different concentrations (100, 200 & 300 μ l) of aqueous extracts of synthesized AgNPs for 24 hours. The maximum mortality range was recorded in 300 μ l of synthesized AgNPs with LC50 26.15 to 44.52 & LC90 22.34 to 42.23 respectively. This study suggests that nanoparticles could be a preferred alternative to the most hazardous existing chemical pesticides, contributing to a healthier environment by providing an ideal ecological and user-friendly vector control strategy for managing malaria and dengue, and contributing to their eventual elimination in the near future.

Keywords: Yellow Fever Mosquito, *Aedes aegypti*, *Andrographis paniculata*, FTIR, AgNPs

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MOLECULAR DOCKING FOR IDENTIFYING EFFECTIVE COMPOUND TARGETING AGAINST BACTERIAL DISEASES OCCURRING IN MARINE FISHES

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ABSTRACT

In this present era, there is an urgent need to search novel Phytoconstituents, their chemical characterization, efficiency and to understand their mechanism of action in order to replace antibiotics and their undesirable side effects. Various bacterial species were causing severe infection diseases in marine aquaculture. The present study reveals the effectiveness of Phytoconstituents extracted from *Caesalpinia bonducella* against marine pathogenic bacterial species *Aeromonashydrophila*, *Renibacterium salmoninarum* and *Lavobacterium psychrophilum* by in-silico prediction and uses of these phytoconstituents in future drug discovery.

Keywords: Novel Phytoconstituents, *Caesalpinia bonducella*, bacterial disease, marine aquaculture

